

Deliverable 4.2

GREAT Case Study Plan

Work Package: WP4 Case Studies and Research Outputs

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This deliverable provides details of the Case Study Design to be applied in the GREAT project. The design is framed in the Methodology Interdisciplinary Research (MIR) Framework (Tobi and Kampen 2018) and this document provides detail of the implementation methods. This consists of an eight-step process of tasks incorporating planning, evaluation and reporting instantiated in a timeline for the GREAT case study programme.
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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DiBL	Dilemma Based Learning
EB	Editorial Board
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
MIR	Methodology Interdisciplinary Research
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides details of the Case Study design methods and process to be deployed in the project. The design incorporates an instantiated eight-stage process consistent with and enhanced Multi Interdisciplinary Research (MIR) framework as previously elaborated in GREAT D4.1. The document provides implementation detail for all stages of the Case Study process with hyperlinks to the required supporting documentation and details of a logic model of evaluation.

The deliverable, which is a public document, is written to support consortium partners in undertaking research activities in the project as its primary audience. It is , however, anticipated that due to the scale-able nature of the design that future iterations of the design could inform future Case Study research in digital domains involving citizen science and where citizen agency is a primary objective.

There is no assumption that all Case studies will conduct **all** stages of the process though cumulatively all stages will be implemented and evaluated over the sum of the GREAT case studies undertaken over the duration of the project.

The Case Study is the primary research instrument deployed in the GREAT project.

2. Introduction

2.1 Case Study as a Research Methodology.

The use of case studies is widely applied in research methodology specifically in the social sciences where holistic in-depth explanations in social behaviour are sought (Zainal, 2007). As an exploratory and explanatory method, it has become prominent when issues (and phenomena) in education (Gulsecen & Kubat, 2006), sociology (Grassel & Schirmer, 2006) and community-based problems (Johnson, 2006) are being examined.

The GREAT project takes a multiple-case design approach. The multiple-case design has been adopted to generate numerous sources of data and evidence through replication as opposed to sampling logic, our rationale being:

- **It is a viable method to elicit implicit and explicit data.**
- **The method is appropriate to the research questions.**
- **Scientific conventions used in social sciences are followed.**
- **A 'chain of evidence', both quantitatively and qualitatively, is systematically recorded.**
- **The examination of data is conducted in the context of its use.**
- **The complexities of the theme could not be captured through the exclusive use of experimental or survey research.**
- **The case study is linked to the theoretical *Methodology Interdisciplinary Research (MIR) Framework (Tobi and Kampen 2018)*.**

'The project will target 6 markets in Europe, to reach a realistic sample of diverse audiences. **Secondly, users for trials will be identified from within the partner organisation and the associate partners**, and particularly from among the students and lecturers of the academic partners. **Thirdly, groups of interested parties will be identified for participation in case studies**, including in playing collaborative games. This third group will make extensive use of the policy stakeholder networks of partners (especially PM, FU and UNIR) and of associate partners.' (pp10 Grant Agreement).

The case study methodology responds to key issues related to climate change and sustainable development issues. This could be to inform policy documents

on climate change, collect data and recommendations that could be applied to support the development of tools, materials, processes and approaches to strengthen the citizen voice and improve engagement. This is in addition to supporting stakeholders' participation in decision making, policy development and action.

The Case study methodology is an open process designed to identify the characteristics to strengthen citizens abilities to act as agents of change.

3. Case Study Design Implementation Method

This section outlines the GREAT method to implement a case study, as of November 2023. It is intended to be a dynamic practical guide and will be reviewed and revised periodically. The guide takes as its starting point the research cycle set out in D4.1 and adapts and expands the components to identify the issues and questions which facilitators need to address, approaches which can be adopted, the outputs of each stage, and the templates and documentation necessary to carry out the activities. Moreover, tasks have also been described for partners to clarify and ease the support of each of the activities in the cycle.

At its current form, a case study comprises 8 activities (represented as circles in Figures 1 and 2) and processes (represented as rectangles). Steps 1 to 3 are supported by WP2 (led by UNIR); Step 4 by WP3 (led by SGI); Steps 5 and 6 by WP4 (led by UoB); and steps 7 and 8 by WP6, led by Playmob. The activities are detailed in Activity Design documents, and exemplars of those conducted at this stage of the project (January 2024) are provided in Annexe 1.

A GREAT research cycle is a whole case study incorporating 8 steps. It is shown in figures 1 and 2 below, in a version showing activities with stakeholders and another showing the support activities carried out by GREAT project partners. It is also available as a stand-alone document [here](#). Once the cycle is started, researchers can repeat a step, or loop back to an earlier step, without this implying the creation of a new case study.

3.1 Planning and reporting

The principal output of the GREAT project will be a methodology for using games-based activities to obtain insight into citizens' views and attitudes on policy dilemmas. Accordingly, it is essential that planning and reporting are carried out for each step using this [planning and reporting template](#). There is also a [guidance document](#) describing how to populate the template. The template is a tool for gathering information, it is not necessary that this be publishable text. Similarly, not all fields will be equally relevant to all steps, and this can be taken into consideration when filling in the template.

In line with the project's agile approach, there is no requirement to stick closely to the plan if circumstances and developments in the case study make it more productive to take a different approach. However, the changes to the plan and the reasons why they were thought to be a good idea should be indicated in the reporting section of the template, in the field provided.

There is a [collection of exemplar activity designs](#) available with at least one activity for each step. These can be adapted as you think best. There is no requirement for them to be used in the case study, they are a support for the case study team. You may not find an activity design which meets your needs, especially in the first case studies carried out, in which case please design your own activity (which is welcome!), the project will create a new activity design based on what you document in the planning and reporting template when the case study has finished. In this way, the collection of activity designs will grow throughout the project.

3.1.1 Evaluation

Evaluation is planned before the start of the case study, according to the procedures set out in this deliverable, and consistent with the project evaluation deliverable (D5.1). The plan will specify which instruments should be used and in which step they should be deployed.

3.1.2 Informed consent

As a requirement, each case study will have been provided with the case study lead academic partner's institutional ethical approval before any of the steps are commenced, and informed consent forms and briefings for participants will be available. The ethical approval documentation will determine in which steps, and how, informed consent needs to be provided. For example, it may be that all the first three steps can be covered by informed consent provided in the first

step. In this case, you should look out for any new participants joining the activities, who will need to complete the informed consent process.

3.1.3 Data

The data to be collected will depend on the activities which are designed for each step. Ensure that it is established how the data will be collected and what tools and information are required to do with it.

The data gathered during the activities in each step will be stored in the folder set up for each case study on the [GREAT NextCloud server](#).

The filenames chosen should indicate.

- The date in format yyyy-mm-dd
- The case study (cs) number assigned before the start of case study.
- The number of the step in which the data was collected.

For example: 2024-02-27_cs3_step6.mp3

Please avoid file formats that require proprietary software. The formats do not need to comply with interoperability standards, but should be widely used formats that can be opened in open-source applications (e.g. docx, jpg, png, mp3, mp4).

3.2 Conduct of a case study

3.2.1 The case study team

Each case study is managed by a team made up of:

- Case study coordinator: a GREAT project member, preferably from the place or organisation where the case study is located, responsible for the practical organisation of the case study.
- Academic lead: a GREAT project member responsible for the rigour of the methodological approach and the scientific outcomes of the case study.
- Case study sponsor: a member of the organisation or stakeholder group that identified the dilemma addressed by the case study, and who will benefit from the results.
- Representatives of stakeholder groups and organisations, as appropriate.

This team should meet at the beginning and end of the case study, and at any moments during the case study that the case study coordinator and academic lead feel is appropriate.

3.2.2 Working with participants.

The GREAT case studies take place in various contexts, with many different types of participants. The case study team will therefore have to consider which approach is most appropriate for working with participants. In particular, the degree to which participants are enthusiastic and/or able to take a significant role in codesigning games-based activities, and in interpreting the outcomes. To the extent that participants are willing, available and capable to take on this role, the work of the case study team will tend towards a facilitation approach, choosing activities which support discussion and consensus between participants. If this is not the case, or only partially so, the case study team may need to take on more of a consultancy role, guiding the participants through structured information-gathering activities, with project members being more active in designing games-based activities and drawing conclusions.

The participants in case studies will be in a wide range of social roles and employment and will have varying types of engagement with the dilemma. This has consequences for the ability to participate in case study activities. Project staff have a research motivation for being involved and are paid. Professional politicians and campaigners are in a similar position. This is not the case for other participants, such as students, members of grassroots organisations or non-affiliated citizens. There is therefore an inequality built into case study activities which could be a barrier to successful completion. However, the principal motivation for participation by citizens and policy stakeholders will be seeing how their opinions and preferences are informing policy decisions. Consequently, great attention should be paid to making this process explicit and communicating progress to participants.

Support

The case study team can obtain support from the project partners.

Each step in the case study cycle is associated with a work package, and the WP leader can provide support, or can recommend a person to respond to requests.

No.	Step	WP	Lead
Step 1	What the case study will achieve and with who	WP2	UNIR
Step 2	Game activity concepts	WP2	UNIR
Step 3	Collaborative design of game activities	WP2	UNIR
Step 4	Games activities with case study participants	WP3	SGI
Step 5	Collaborative data analysis	WP4	UoB
Step 6	Conclusions and evaluation	WP4	UoB
Step 7	Community engagement	WP6	Playmob
Step 8	Policy stakeholder engagement	WP6	Playmob

Table 1. The Case Study Steps

Additionally, evaluation work across the case study is the responsibility of WP5, led by ZSI and overall responsibility for the case studies lies with WP4, led by UoB.

4. GREAT research cycle into practice: the tasks of stakeholders and partners

This section aims to put the GREAT Research Method into practice. The research method elaborates the method detailed in D4.1 informed iteratively as the processes are enacted.

Figure 1 presents a comprehensive overview of the activities involved in the process, along with the corresponding processes for stakeholders. Similarly, Figure 2 depicts these activities and processes specifically for partners. By providing these visual representations, we aim to offer a holistic understanding of the process, facilitating a smooth initiation of the case study.

Figure 1. GREAT Case Study Cycle Stakeholders

Figure 2. GREAT Case Study Cycle Partners

4.1 Step 1: What the case study will achieve and with who.

Participating stakeholders will join a workshop or equivalent activities to identify and prioritise the research topics. Typically, this is a workshop to work on defining what the case study will achieve and with who will be carried out. In this step, stakeholders will be asked to:

- Identify a current issue related to the climate emergency which creates a policy dilemma for the stakeholders involved in the case study.
- Describe the opinions and attitudes of citizens which would contribute to resolving the policy dilemma.
- Identify citizens' specific choices, preferences, or actions ('indicators') that could provide evidence to help resolve the dilemma and how they could be observed?"
- Consider which specific stakeholder groups would need to be involved in the games-based activities to gather the opinions and attitudes needed to make progress on the policy dilemma. Ideally, these should be named organisations or groups of people, rather than abstract categories of stakeholder.

Partners will contribute as follows:

- Choose the tool(s) that will be used to support the workshop. Partners will also have to set them up and prepare them for the workshop.
- Select or adapt an [activity design](#), or create a new one.
- Complete the planning section of the [planning and reporting template](#), and once the step has been completed, the reporting section. Consider consulting the [guidance](#) on how to use the planning and reporting template.
- Facilitate the activities: explain each step, provide the needed information, and support all the participants to ensure that all perspectives are included in identifying the selected dilemma.
- Depending on the particular group of stakeholders involved, and the issues addressed, it may be necessary to help stakeholders to understand what information is already available about climate emergency policy issues in general, or related to the particular policy issue that they are interested in.

Additional considerations:

Bullet Point 4 of the participating stakeholder activities, above (the specific stakeholders who can provide the required information), may already have been addressed (or partially so) in the set-up of the case study. It is particularly important to know what groups of people can be expected to participate in any developed DIBL game. If it is not possible to specify the groups of participants in this activity, this can be firmed up in follow-up conversations or message exchanges.

The outcome of this step is a design challenge. It consists of a statement of:

- the policy dilemma to be addressed in the case study.
- the insight into the problem which the case study sponsor(s) would like to obtain.
- The opinions or preferences of the stakeholders which would (directly or indirectly) indicate their position on the dilemma.
- the social group(s) and organisations which will be engaged as stakeholders in the case study.

4.2 Step 2: Game activity concepts

Participating stakeholders will join a workshop or equivalent activities to generate ideas for the game activity. To do this, the stakeholders will:

- Define a scenario that would encourage participants in a game or survey to share the information needed to address the policy dilemma.
- Think of things that could happen in a serious game that could stimulate the generation of the information needed to address the dilemma. Alternatively (or as well), think of questions that you would like to ask the stakeholders who were identified in Step 1.
- Decide if it is necessary to gather, or author, documents or media which explain the scenario, or help to imagine it.
- Think about what data can be gathered in the scenario that has been identified, where it will come from, and what could be done with it.
- Plan a timeframe when the games-based activities could be carried out.

Partners will contribute as follows:

- The work in Step 2 should build on the design brief created in Step 1. Ensure you have the design brief available and remind the participants about what was decided. Remember that it is possible that there will be participants in Step 2 who were not involved in Step 1.
- Select an [activity design](#) and customise it, if needed, or create a new one.
- Select and set up any tools needed in the activity design, adding any necessary information to them, and providing credentials for participants, when needed.
- Complete the planning section of the [planning and reporting template](#), and once the step has been completed, the reporting section. Consider consulting the [guidance](#) on how to use the planning and reporting template.
- Guide the activity process, informing about steps to be developed, giving access to the tools and, in general, facilitating the run of the activity.

Additional considerations:

Participants may find it challenging to understand what is meant by a scenario. It may be helpful to think of it in terms of a concept for a reality show or an improvised drama.

For Bullet point 2 of the stakeholder activities in this step, above, you should be familiar with the two technical platforms used by GREAT:

- DIBL, provided by partner SGI, creates 'serious games' for small groups of people to play. You can think of this as a kind of structured focus group.
- Playmob, which inserts quiz games into popular mobile games. This is a kind of survey.

You may already know if you will use both, or one or the other. This will depend in part on the stakeholders engaging in the games-based activities, which may have been discussed when the case study was set up. Depending on the knowledge and skills of the participants, you should discuss the technical platforms to be used at this stage, which will move forward the case study design. However, it is also possible to leave open the question of the technical platform, and to decide on this in follow up discussions and message exchanges. These considerations will have a strong influence on the design of activities for Step 2.

4.3 Step 3: Collaborative design of game activities

Participating stakeholders will engage in activities to co-create a story, the narrative for a DIBL serious game, and/or the questions and deployment strategy for a Playmob quiz.

For a DIBL game:

- They will describe the dilemma in sufficient detail to provide a compelling situation for the participants in the game.
- Decide on the interactions that occur during the game
- Decide how resources about the dilemma (e.g. text descriptions, photos, web links, videos) will be used (if any).

For a Playmob survey

- They will finalise the precise questions that will be included in the survey.
- Decide on a strategy for embedding the survey in a game.
- Decide on the geographical context for the delivery of the game.
- Provide input for any external web pages that will be linked to from the Playmob quiz. These will be used for evaluation purposes, but can also

collect additional data (e.g. free text statements of participants' opinions).

Partners in the GREAT project will help by:

- Select an [activity design](#) and customise it, if needed, or create a new one.
- Complete the planning section of the [planning and reporting template](#), and once the step has been completed, the reporting section. Consider consulting the [guidance](#) on how to use the planning and reporting template.
- Coordinate with the teams in Playmob and/or SGI to plan activities on or for their platforms, set up tools, and provide credentials, if needed.
- Facilitate collaborative activities and provide technical support as required.
- Complete the [planning and reporting template](#): a planning and report template is available to plan each activity and, once finalised, report about it.

Additional Considerations:

It is important that participants and stakeholders do not think that they are being asked to develop the final games. They should understand that additional game design work will be carried out by GREAT staff. This should be made clear in briefings for this step (including at the end of Step 2).

Planning and Reporting:

At this stage of the development of the case study process it is essential that the study activities, outcomes and objectives are directly address the overarching research objectives and questions as detailed below and elaborated in GREAT D4.1. It is not anticipated that all cases will cover all questions.

<p>1. To establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policymakers.</p>	
<p>RQ 1.1: Which methods in digital games can be used to create an information exchange between attitudes and preferences of citizens on societal challenges (e.g., climate change) and policy makers working on these challenges?</p> <p>RQ 1.2: How effective and efficient is the use of games in creating an information exchange between attitudes and preferences of citizens on societal challenges (e.g. climate change) and policy makers?</p> <p>RQ 1.3: How can games be used to foster dialogue and collaboration on societal challenges (e.g. climate change)?</p>	
<p>2. To understand the actual and potential impact that games can have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences.</p>	
<p>RQ 2.1: What are the affordances of games in developing citizens' engagement with challenges and dilemmas arising from societal challenges like climate crisis.</p> <p>RQ 2.2: What are the affordances of games in informing policy on the societal challenges like climate crisis.</p> <p>RQ 2.3: What is the value to policy stakeholder groups of the information on citizens' attitudes and preferences generated through games-based activities?</p> <p>RQ 2.4: What is the value to citizens of enabling them to engage in policy discourse through the design of and engagement in games-based activities?</p>	

<p>RQ 2.5: How generalisable are the GREAT methods to other global challenges or other fields of research and innovation?</p>	
<p>3. To provide practical guidance for games developers and policy stakeholders.</p>	
<p>RQ 3.1: Which are the key interventions in the GREAT method which lead to its effectiveness and efficiency? RQ 3.2: Which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting the method to new contexts? RQ 3.3: What documentation and/or training is required for games developers, policy stakeholder groups</p>	
<p>4. To assess the benefits and risks to individuals and society of using games to promote engagement with societal challenges.</p>	
<p>Research Question 4.1: What are the benefits and risks experienced by citizen participants, policy stakeholders, games designers and providers, as well as policy makers and organizations, when they participate in the GREAT method?</p>	

Table 2. Research Questions

4.4 Step 4: Games activities with case study participants

In this step, games-based activities with case study participants are carried out. Stakeholders who are participating in the design and implementation of the case study do not need to carry out any activities in this step, as these will be carried out by GREAT partners. The stakeholder groups identified in step one will participating in the DIBL games and will receive invitations to respond to Playmob surveys.

Partners in the GREAT project will:

- Set up, run, and facilitate one or both of:

A DIBL game or games. In this case, it will be necessary to know from Step 1 which specific groups of stakeholders will participate, and to coordinate with them to arrange how the game will be played, which people will participate, and how they can be contacted.

A Playmob survey, following the procedures set out by Playmob.

- Monitor and manage data gathering and storage during the established timeframe.
- Complete the [planning and reporting template](#): a planning and report template is available to plan each of the activities and, once finalised, report about it.

4.5 Step 5. Collaborative data analysis

Participating stakeholders will participate in a workshop or similar collaborative activities to:

- Interpret the data obtained from games activities.
- Collaborating with partners and stakeholders assess the value of the data and the possible need for further data collection.

Project partners will:

- Select an [activity design](#) and customise it, if needed, or create a new one.
- Select and set up any tools needed in the activity design, adding any necessary information to them, and providing credentials for participants, when needed.
- Complete the planning section of the [planning and reporting template](#), and once the step has been completed, the reporting section. Consider consulting the [guidance](#) on how to use the planning and reporting template.
- Process data obtained from Step 4 "Games activities with case study participants" and provision dashboards or other data representations provided by WP3.
- Facilitate collaborative analysis activities involving both GREAT partners and participating stakeholders to identify the conclusions that can be drawn from the data.
- Assess if further data collection is needed. If so, determine the items missing and plan how they will be obtained (which means planning a

repeat of step 4, and possibly also of step 3), It Additional Considerations:

- Depending on the activity design used in this step, and on the availability, skills and willingness of participants, GREAT staff may need to carry out a greater or lesser amount of data analysis.

It is anticipated that the qualitative data will be analysed using MaxQDA, a qualitative data analysis tool following the procedures set out in (Saldaña, 2021). Semi-structured interviews with individual participants and focus groups will uncover their attitudes and thoughts relating to key themes, topics and issues, expectations, and touch points for interacting with the game. Secondly, their experiences and the links between behaviours and emotions around the themes and the game. Interviews and focus groups will be carried out both face-to-face and remotely. This will enable the project to confirm engagement with diverse audiences and ensure comprehension of the theme/question sets. It will also reveal the audience's understanding of specific themes relating to the climate crisis and how these themes relate to them, and their motivations to help tackle the crisis (e.g. whether they are driven by creating a better world for their children, cost savings, money making, or because it's on trend, etc.).

The transcriptions of player interactions in the DIBL games will be a valuable resource. Quantitative data will be collected from the logs of the games, and through the Playmob platform, providing the input for the analytics carried out. The project will apply state-of-the-art statistical and machine learning techniques, and design data analysis processes and algorithms which can transform the data from the games into valuable inputs for policy stakeholders.

4.6 Step 6: Conclusions and evaluation

Participating stakeholders will:

- Collaboratively formulate the conclusions that can be drawn from the results of Step 5. The conclusions should address the expected insight and evidence into the policy dilemma formulated in step 1.
- Provide feedback on the case-study process and participate in the evaluation.

Project partners will:

- Select an [activity design](#) and customise it, if needed, or create a new one.

- Select and set up any tools needed in the activity design, adding any necessary information to them, and providing credentials for participants, when needed.
- Complete the planning section of the [planning and reporting template](#), and once the step has been completed, the reporting section. Consider consulting the [guidance](#) on how to use the planning and reporting template. Populate the activity design document with information obtained from “5. Collaborative data analysis” step.
- Facilitate a workshop or other collaborative activity in which:
 - The policy implications of the results of the data analysis in Step 5 are explored.
 - Policy guidance and recommendations are formulated.
 - Document the policy insights which are identified.
 - Depending on the activity design used in this step, and on the availability, skills and willingness of participants, GREAT staff may need to carry out a more or less leading role in defining policy guidance and recommendations.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of the method, in accordance with the evaluation plan for the case study as a whole, which will have been developed according to the processes described in D4.2.
- Complete [planning and reporting template](#): we have a planning and report template to plan each of the activities and, once finalised, report about it.

4.7 Step 7: Community engagement

Participating stakeholders

- Suggest appropriate community engagement activities that are impacted by the policy dilemma.
- Identify dissemination opportunities.
- When appropriate, collaborate with GREAT project partners in community engagement and dissemination activities.

The GREAT case study team meanwhile, will:

- Prepare dissemination materials.
- Disseminate dissemination materials using posts in the GREAT project website, presentations in events, webinars.
- Publicise on selected GREAT channels and networks, according to the GREAT dissemination plan.

- Obtain feedback from the wider community of stakeholders, not only those involved in case study activities, according to the measures described in the case study evaluation plan and the GREAT dissemination plan.
- Finalise the [planning and reporting template](#): we have a planning and report template to plan each of the activities.

Additional comments:

- Dissemination and community engagement activities should include both the conclusions of data analysis from Step 5 and the policy conclusions from Step 6.
- Face-to-face community engagement activities are encouraged, as are synchronous virtual events.
- Dissemination should be tailored to a variety of audiences. Those who participated in the surveys, the wider public, policy makers and as project outputs.

Appropriate dissemination methods include web posts, events, presentations, webinars or social networks. Dissemination procedures are set out in the dissemination plan

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/16Re7okvroXkhboBy2sqhj8rwQa_ePzI4, but additional dissemination measures are also welcome.

- Information should be kept about all community engagement and dissemination activities. It is also important to seek and take advantage of opportunities for feedback from stakeholders.

4.8 Step 8: Policy stakeholder engagement

In this final activity, the goal is to close the cycle by engaging with policy stakeholders, and in particular the policymakers who identified the dilemma addressed by the case study. Participating stakeholders, and particularly the sponsors who identified the dilemma addressed by the case study, should expect to:

- Attend a presentation of the insight report and read it.
- Provide feedback on the insight report and/or complete an evaluation form.
- Report briefly on possible application of the findings in the insight report.
- Participate in a follow-up dialogue with other stakeholders if this is valuable and feasible.
- Inform the synthesis of findings with reports and policies with the objective of enriching policy and the ongoing dialogue on climate change.

To support these activities, the partners will:

- Create a concise and accessible insight report, based on the results of step 6.
- Present the case study results to the policy makers who identified the dilemma.
- Disseminate the insight report to policy makers and stakeholders who face the same (or a similar) dilemma but were not involved in the case study.
- Obtain feedback from case study stakeholders, according to the evaluation plan.
- Set up dialogue policy makers and stakeholders, if this is valuable to the participants.
- Complete [planning and reporting template](#) for this step.

4. GREAT Case Study Evaluation, Planning and Reporting

The GREAT case study evaluation and reporting is overseen by partner ZSI (WP5 Lead Partner), who have developed guidance documents and a protocol as detailed below:

- Case Study representatives will discuss the study with ZSI to ensure alignment of the evaluation instruments to be deployed in advance of the implementation of the case study.
- ZSI will provide support and detail the evaluation instruments for data collection; please note that you may have to adapt the instrument in terms of language or contextual setting (i.e., develop translations or make language more accessible). As this may take some time, it is important that as a case study leader you get in contact with ZSI as soon as possible in the case study design process.

4.1 Evaluation designs

Evaluation Designs have been developed for each scenario or case study, the selection of evaluation Design is undertaken by the Case Study leaders and evaluation partner ZSI to ensure the appropriate designs are deployed.

Three evaluation designs are provided below tailored to specific stakeholder groups and activities these being; Player participants of the Playmob quiz games, Player participants of the dilemma (DiBL) games and in the broader citizen science activities associated with the project. The logic model designs incorporate the key aspects required to effectively evaluate the activities Design, Outcomes, Measures and Materials. Further details regarding the evaluation activities underpinning these diagrams is provided in the accompanying GREAT deliverable D5.1.

4. 1.1. Evaluation design for (Playmob) quiz games

Figure 3. Research Design for assessing participants playing the quiz game

4.1.2. Evaluation design for dilemma games

Figure 4. Research Design for assessing participants playing the dilemma game

4. 1.3. evaluation design for other citizen science activities in the case study

Figure 5. Research Design for assessing participants involved in citizen science activities

5. Planned Case Study Timeline

The schedule and referencing for the planned Case Studies is detailed in the GREAT project grant agreement; iterative development allows for revisions informed by recognition of the pragmatic observations undertaken during the implementation process.

6. References

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